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LAMINATED COMPOSITE FLANGE DESIGN
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ABSTRACT

In this paper a parametric model has been developed for the optimum design of laminated composite flanges. The study focuses on the evaluation and performance optimization of composite flanges with the optimum selection of material system, layup pattern and gore strip angle. The effect of butt-joint between the gore strips is also evaluated. Two dimensional laminate field theory and maximum stress failure criteria are employed in the analysis. The results are presented with the aid of plots showing the effects of gore angle, start angle and layup pattern on the final design. The accuracy of the model is verified through a series of coupon specimen tests with different ply layup patterns and with and without the butt joint. The experimental results agree very well with the numerical predictions.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the last two decades there has been phenomenal development in the analytical capability to analyze the behavior of composite materials and their structural elements like beams, plates and shells. However, there is a lack of design models which may be readily utilized for the design of various structural components, especially under complex loading conditions. Due to the complexity of the geometry and the loading conditions, existing theories and analytical tools need to be tailored to the form of specific engineering models to suit the design of particular structural components. This paper is concerned with the development of a model for the optimum design of laminated composite flange for the connection of aerospace ducts. The design methodology, however, will remain the same for composite flanges on other applications. Use of laminated composite flanges (Fig. 1) and ducts

in aerospace applications has shown the advantage of weight reduction and more effective resistance to applied loads. The fabrication method employed for lamination of composite flanges requires the assembly of several identical pieces of gore strips to form a sublayer of the flange. The gore strips are cut from a large size unidirectional angle ply and, therefore, the fibers are not continuous at the intersection (butt-joint) between two gore strips. Moreover, the fiber orientation of each layer changes as a function of circumferential location, and thus the material properties vary from position to position. Also, with the existence of a butt-joint, complex stress states with a rapid change of stress gradients occur at the butt-joint location due to geometrical discontinuity. The abrupt change of material properties within the laminate further increases the design complexities [11]. Many theories have been proposed in the past two decades to analyze the stress field in composite laminates [4,5,6,10]. In general, for practical engineering structural design using laminated composite, if the thickness-to-side ratio is small, classical laminate theory, is adequate to provide quite accurate design analysis [4,6,9] and therefore is widely used in engineering composite design work [1,8].

The study, in this paper, focuses on the evaluation and performance optimization of composite flanges with the optimum selection of material system, layup pattern and gore strip angle. The effect of butt-joint between the gore strips and the effect of start angle are also evaluated. Two dimensional laminate field theory and maximum stress failure criteria are employed in the analysis. Finally the accuracy of the model is verified through a series of coupon specimen tests with different ply layup patterns and with or without the butt joint.

2. GEOMETRIC MODELING

Design variables for a laminated composite flange (as shown in Fig. 1) include gore angle, start angle, ideal angle, location angle, butt-joint location, layup pattern, flange dimensions, applied loads and types of composite material. Two geometric modeling are involved in this analysis; (1) single layer modeling and (2) laminate modeling.

2.1 Single Layer Modeling For a single layer in a laminated composite flange, which is made of N pieces of identical gore strips cut from an unidirectional angle lamina (see Fig. 1), the fiber angle at the middle circumferential location of gore strip is the same as the unidirectional angle of lamina and is defined as ideal angle (IDA) here in order not to be confused with the fiber angle which is varied along the circumferential location. The gore strips are layed up at any start angle (SA) to form a

layer. The fiber angle at any circumferential location can be determined by the following equations.

(1) At circumferential location AB, rotating β degree counter-clockwise from the middle of gore strip, the fiber angle is

$$FA = IDA + \beta \quad (1a)$$

(2) At circumferential location CD, rotating α degree clockwise from the middle of gore strip, the fiber angle is

$$FA = IDA - \alpha \quad (1b)$$

2.2 Laminate Modeling The geometrical characteristic of the laminated flange is the combination of layers with different ideal angle and start angle as described in the previous section. Its typical in-plane configuration is also shown in Fig. 1. In combining plate theory with laminate theory, assumption is made that each composite lamina can be analyzed as a thin plate. For each lamina of the flange, the stress-strain relation is [3]

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{\theta} \\ \sigma_r \\ \sigma_{r\theta} \end{Bmatrix}^k = [Q]^k \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{\theta} \\ \epsilon_r \\ \epsilon_{r\theta} \end{Bmatrix}^k \quad (2)$$

and the classical constitutive equations of a laminate is

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_{\theta} \\ N_r \\ N_{r\theta} \\ M_{\theta} \\ M_r \\ M_{r\theta} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ & & A_{66} & B_{61} & B_{62} & B_{66} \\ & & & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ & \text{symm.} & & & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ & & & & & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{\theta}^o \\ \epsilon_r^o \\ \epsilon_{r\theta}^o \\ K_{\theta} \\ K_r \\ K_{r\theta} \end{Bmatrix}$$

or

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ \text{---} \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ \text{---} & \text{---} \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^o \\ \text{---} \\ K \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where [A] = Extensional stiffness matrix
 [B] = Coupling matrix
 [D] = Flexural stiffness matrix

3. STRESS/MOMENT RESULTANTS

The flange is designed for connecting two ducts and will be subjected to

internal pressure, bending moment and torque transferred from the ducts. The stress/moment resultants due to these loads are presented in the following.

(i) Stress resultant due to internal pressure

The stresses of a hollow cylinder subjected to internal pressure (P_1) are given by [12], and the stress resultants N_r and N_θ distributed circumferentially over the flange cross section are

$$N_r = \frac{R_1^2 P_1}{R_o^2 - R_1^2} \left(1 - \frac{R_o^2}{r^2} \right) \times t$$

$$N_\theta = \frac{R_1^2 - p_1}{R_o^2 - R_1^2} \left(1 + \frac{R_o^2}{r^2} \right) \times t \quad (4)$$

$$N_{r\theta} = 0$$

where R_o and R_1 are the outer and inner radii of the flange respectively.

(ii) Moment resultant due to bending moment and torque

The moment resultants M_T and M_r due to bending moment (BM) applied to the flange are

$$M_T = \frac{BM}{2 R_1} \times \left(\frac{R_o - R_1}{2} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$M_r = \frac{BM \times (R_o - R_1)}{8 \pi R_1^2}$$

and the moment resultant due to torque (T) applied to the flange is

$$M_{r\theta} = \frac{T}{2 \pi R_1} \quad (6)$$

4. DESIGN PROCEDURE

An interactive computer program was developed to obtain the optimal flange design parameters. Initially, geometrical dimensions of flange, loading conditions, layup configuration and types of material are input to the program. The program then starts to increase the number of layers and, at each layer increment, calculates the corresponding stress states at each location angle of the flange. Finally, the required minimum number of layers is obtained when all the calculated stress states at each location angle satisfy the failure criterion.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the following, for demonstration purpose, selected numerical results of different layup patterns under a given loading condition are presented and discussed. AS-4397 graphite epoxy fiber reinforced composite and applied loads of internal pressure, $P_1=72$ psi, bending moment, $M=437,600$ lb-in, and torque, $T=10,000$ lb-in were used in this numerical analysis. The material properties of AS-4397 and polymer (matrix) PMR 15 are listed in Table 1. Four layup patterns, 0/90, 30/-30, 45/-45, and 0/45/-45/0 were analyzed and four gore strip angles were selected for evaluation. Since fiber angle and stiffness matrix vary along the flange circumferential location, the number of layers required at each circumferential location will differ as well. If butt-joint effect is taken into consideration, material properties at the butt-joint location are set to equal matrix properties. Results of required layers for each layup pattern are shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

As shown in Fig. 2, for 0/45/-45/0 layup pattern, 15-degree gore angle is the best choice whereas 60-degree gore angle is the worst one, and the total number of layers required increased with the increase of gore angles, with or without considering the butt-joint effect. Fig. 3 shows pieces versus layer plots which were obtained by combining the figures similar to Fig. 2 for every layup pattern and gore angle. For 0/90 layup pattern with 60-degree gore angle, the number of layer required increases from 64 to 124 if the effect of butt-joint is considered. For layup pattern of 30/-30, if butt-joint effect is taken into consideration, the total number of layers required is the same for the four gore angles considered, i.e. critical location is at the butt joint location. For layup pattern of 45/-45, the trend is the same as that of layup pattern of 30/-30, i.e. total layers required are the same for the four gore angles considered and the critical location is at the butt joint. In general, 15-degree gore strip requires the least number of layer and is the best choice. For gore angle of 15, 30 and 45 degrees, the best layup pattern is 0/90 while for gore angle of 60 degrees layup pattern of 30/-30 will be the better choice. All these results are based on letting the start angle equal to half of the gore angle. We also investigated the effect of start angle for 0/45/-45/0 layup pattern and the results showed that there is no effect on the layers required (Fig. 4). This conclusion is valid for other layup patterns except for 15-degree gore strip with 0/90 layup pattern (Fig. 5).

6. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

Coupon specimens with different layup patterns were prepared and tested to failure to determine the load-carrying capacity of each layup pattern and compare with the numerical predictions. The numerically calculated failure load is updated as follows: (1) if no ply damage is predicted the applied

load is increased by some predetermined load increment, (2) if plies are damaged or destroyed, the same load is applied with reduced material properties assigned to the damaged layers. This iterative procedure continues until the total fracture of the laminate. Coupon specimens were cut from graphite epoxy PMC plates, IM7/CE9200, and the material properties are shown in Table 1. The laminate layup configurations are shown in Table 2. Specimen were tabbed at each end with aluminum tabs and tested under uniaxial tension which simulates the flange subjected to internal pressure. The experimental results are presented in Table 2 and the corresponding load-deflection curves are shown in Figs. 6 thru 8. The experimental results agree very well with the numerical predictions.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this investigation, based on classical laminate theory and maximum stress failure criterion, a parametric model was developed for predicting the strength of laminated composite flange subjected to combined external loads. An interactive computer program was developed as a design tool that can provide the following information and advantages:

- (i) The program takes into account the loading conditions, variations of gore angles, start angles, location angles, layup patterns, butt-joint effect, flange dimensions and types of composite material for on-line optimum design of laminated composite flange.
- (ii) The pieces versus layers plots (Fig. 3) can be used as a guideline for designer to determine and choose the best layup configuration for optimum performance and minimum fabrication cost.
- (iii) The design code is capable of designing laminated composite flange in the presence of butt joint.

Although only limited layup configurations and one loading condition were presented in this analysis, the design program can be easily extended to more sophisticated configurations and other loading conditions.

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9. BIOGRAPHY

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Table 1 Composite Material Properties

Property	AS-4397	IM7/CE9220	PMR 15	CE9220
Ex	125.9 GPa	137.8 GPa	3.24 GPa	8.27 GPa
Ey	9.6 GPa	8.3 GPa	3.24 GPa	8.27 GPa
Gxy	7.1 GPa	4.8 GPa	1.65 GPa	4.82 GPa
ν_{xy}	0.3	0.35	0.36	0.37
Xt	1339 MPa	2025 MPa	55.1 MPa	55.1 MPa
Xc	1419 MPa	1378 MPa	110 MPa	165 MPa
Yt	37 MPa	55.1 MPa	55.1 MPa	55.1 MPa
Yc	206 MPa	165 MPa	110 MPa	165 MPa
S	93 MPa	96.5 MPa	55.1 MPa	96.5 MPa

Table 2 Coupon test results

Specimen	Layup Pattern	Est. Load	Expt. Load
1	45/-45B/45	210 lb	220 lb
2	45/-45/-45B/45	480 lb	520 lb
3	45/-45/-45/45	510 lb	500 lb

* B indicates butt joint in the layer

Fig. 1 A typical laminated composite flange

(a) With butt-joint effect

(b) Without butt-joint effect

Fig. 2 Layers versus location angle plots for 0/45/-45/0 layup pattern

(a) With butt-joint effect

(b) Without butt-joint effect

Fig. 3 Pieces required versus number of layers plots

Fig. 4 Layers versus start angle plots for 0/45/-45/0 layup pattern

Fig. 5 Layers versus start angle plots for 0/90 layup pattern

Fig. 6 Load versus deflection plots for 45/-45B/45 layup pattern

Fig. 7 Load versus deflection plots for 45/-45B/-45/45 layup pattern

Fig. 8 Load versus deflection plots for 45/-45/-45/45 layup pattern